

Methodology: Developing Eligibility and Selection Criteria

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

Purpose of this document

This document explains how the eligibility and selection criteria for DC4NES training seats were developed. It is published alongside the criteria documents as a transparency and accountability record. All documents are available on Zenodo under the Digital Capacity for NES community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes> and linked to the 4TU.ResearchData website.

Guiding principles

The criteria were developed with the following principles in mind:

- Openness: the process is documented and publicly available.
- Inclusivity: criteria are designed to lower barriers to participation, particularly for institutions and individuals not currently connected to the Carpentries NL network.
- Representativeness: the distribution of seats should reflect the geographic and institutional diversity of the NES domain in the Netherlands.
- Sustainability: preference is given to candidates and teams likely to remain active contributors to the Carpentries NL community beyond the project period.

How the criteria were developed

Collaborative proposal writing

During the TDCC-NES proposal writing stage, the Carpentries Coordinators held a hybrid information session (online and in-person at the Netherlands eScience Center) on the 31 October 2024, to gather a first round of feedback from the community. We had just over 20 participants, mainly coming from local digital competence centers. The input was incorporated into the main proposal and included ideas for eligibility and selection criteria; these were also included as questions in the survey that was circulated in late 2025 (more on that below).

Desk review

The project team reviewed the project proposal, the TDCC-NES roadmap, and existing Carpentries NL community documentation to identify initial criteria. This included reviewing the distribution of existing certified instructors, institutional membership status, and geographic gaps in training provision.

Project kick-off meeting

During the DC4NES project initiation meeting, project partners and members of the Carpentries Coordinators Network NL proposed and discussed initial criteria. Key considerations included:

- NES domain affiliation as a core eligibility requirement. Of the 50 Instructor seats, at least 50% are reserved for candidates affiliated with an NES domain

or NES-affiliated department. The remaining seats are open to candidates from other research domains.

- Contract type as a selection criterion. The project aims for at least 50% of all trained instructors to hold permanent contracts and at least 25% for temporary staff.
- Exclusion of institutions already holding Carpentries membership with instructor training seats.
- Regional distribution as a selection criterion.
- A two-step approach (nomination and open call) for instructor training seats.

Community survey

A survey was distributed to the broader research community (including members belonging to the NES domain) to gather input on:

- Estimated demand for instructor training per institution and region.
- Perceived fairness of proposed eligibility and selection criteria.
- Interest in lesson development activities.
- Existing digital skills training initiatives that may overlap with or complement DC4NES activities.

Survey reports are published on Zenodo and on the 4TU.ResearchData project page. The results informed the finalization of the criteria.

Consultation with the Carpentries Coordinators Network NL

Draft criteria were reviewed and refined by the Carpentries Coordinators Network NL, who also serve as the selection committee for oversubscribed calls.

Version control

All criteria documents are versioned and stored on Zenodo. Any revisions to criteria between calls will be documented with a change log and rationale.